

1 **Assessment of cross-flow filtration as microalgae harvesting**
2 **technique prior to anaerobic digestion: evaluation of biomass**
3 **integrity and energy demand.**

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12 **Abstract**

13 In the present study, the effect of cross-flow filtration (CFF) on the overall
14 valorization of *Chlorella spp.* microalgae as biogas was assessed. The effect of CFF on
15 microalgae cell integrity was quantified in terms of viability which was correlated with
16 the anaerobic biodegradability. The viability dropped as the biomass concentration
17 increased, whereas anaerobic biodegradability increased linearly with the viability
18 reduction. It was hypothesized that a stress-induced release and further accumulation
19 of organic polymers during CFF increased the flux resistance which promoted harsher
20 shear-stress conditions. Furthermore, the volume reduction as the concentration
21 increased entailed an increase in the specific energy supply to the biomass. The energy

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1 demand was positive in the whole range of concentrations studied, yielding an overall
2 energy efficiency as high as 22.9 % for the highest concentration studied. Specifically,
3 heat requirements were lower than electricity requirements only when the biomass
4 concentrations exceeded 10 g COD·L⁻¹.

5 **Keywords:** harvesting; cross-flow filtration; microalgae integrity; anaerobic
6 biodegradability; energy balance.

7 **1 INTRODUCTION**

8 Microalgae biomass is regarded as a promising feedstock for biofuels
9 production, since it has a higher growth yield compared to terrestrial crops (Li et al.,
10 2008) and it can be cultivated in marginal land preventing the competition with food
11 crops for arable land (Singh and Gu, 2010). In addition, microalgae can be grown using
12 wastewater as a water and nutrients source, reporting a double benefit: avoiding
13 intensive use of fertilizers for microalgae growth whilst polishing wastewater (Park et
14 al., 2011). Furthermore, microalgae can capture as much as 1.83 kg CO₂·kg⁻¹ VS that
15 can contribute to relieve the global warming (Brennan and Owende, 2010; Lam and
16 Lee, 2012).

17 In contrast, microalgae cultures usually have low cell density (less than 0.1 %
18 w/v) and concentration up to a certain degree, depending on downstream
19 applications, is generally required. Depending on the final concentration degree
20 achieved, the concentration step can be classified as harvesting (1-7 %) or thickening
21 (7-20 %) (Pragya et al., 2013). Further dewatering might be required for some
22 applications (e.g. lipids extraction). Unfortunately, microalgae suspensions are very
23 stable due to their negatively charged surface, which hampers the use of gravity
24 sedimentation (Danquah et al., 2009). Indeed, a both economically viable and efficient

1 microalgae concentration does not exist so far (Barros et al., 2015). Alternatively,
2 techniques entailing whether an intensive use of reagents (e.g., flocculation, flotation
3 and gravity sedimentation) or energy (e.g., centrifugation or membrane filtration) are
4 normally applied, which can contribute up to one-third to the total microalgae biomass
5 production cost (Estime et al., 2017). Therefore, concentration is regarded as the
6 major bottleneck in the microalgae biomass production process, and still prevents
7 microalgae from being used as feedstock for several purposes (Gross, 2013; Lardon et
8 al., 2009; Singh et al., 2013).

9 Anaerobic transformation into biogas is a suitable approach for microalgae-
10 derived biofuels production, since virtually all the macromolecules in microalgae
11 (lipids, proteins and sugars) can be anaerobically degraded. Unlike lipids extraction
12 process for biodiesel production, biomethane can be produced via wet anaerobic
13 digestion, so concentration of biomass can be avoided. Nevertheless, the
14 concentration of biomass will affect anaerobic digestion in different ways. On the one
15 hand, working with dilute cultures entails the handling of large culture-media volumes.
16 Therefore, the required reactor working volume will be proportionally big, since the
17 slow kinetics of anaerobic processes makes high solids retention times necessary
18 (Giménez et al., 2011). The use of a biomass retention system (i.e. physical barriers,
19 reactor configuration) would enable to decouple the hydraulic retention time from the
20 solids retention time, making it possible to treat bigger volumes in smaller reactors,
21 since the high solids concentration achieved can offset the slow kinetics. However, a
22 high amount of energy would still be necessary to warm the biomass up, as long as the
23 digester is operated in the mesophilic or thermophilic range of temperatures whereas
24 microalgae are operated in a lower temperature range (15-25°C). Additionally, the

1 effluent of the anaerobic digestion is, at least, saturated with methane, depending on
2 the mass transfer conditions prevailing within the reactor (Giménez et al., 2012).
3 Methane is both a greenhouse gas (GHG) with a global warming potential over 100
4 years of 28-36 (IPCC, 2014) and a high heating-value fuel, so both environmental and
5 energetic issues are linked to its free emission to the atmosphere with the effluent. As
6 a powerful GHG, methane must be removed from the effluent. To this regard,
7 dissolved methane recovery with membrane contactors has been proved energetically
8 efficient (Cookney et al., 2016; Crone et al., 2017; Henares et al., 2017), even though a
9 fraction of the potential energy in the dissolved methane has to be devoted to the
10 recovery of the dissolved methane itself. Therefore, the higher the volume to be
11 treated, the higher the energetic loss in the system.

12 On the other hand, the cell wall of some microalgae is made up of complex
13 carbohydrates which feature high resistance against anaerobic biodegradability
14 (González-Fernández et al., 2013). The anaerobic biodegradability of microalgae is
15 usually hampered by its cell wall, which acts as a protecting barrier that prevents
16 anaerobic microorganisms to reach the inner organic compounds. A number of
17 pretreatment techniques have been developed which are successful at breaking down
18 microalgae cell wall, enabling inner organic compounds to be available to anaerobic
19 organisms (Passos et al., 2014a). There are some literature references (Carrere et al.,
20 2016; Kim et al., 2012; Li et al., 2012) reporting an effect of the biomass concentration
21 on the pretreatment efficiency. In some cases, as in thermal pretreatment, the
22 concentration degree will have a direct effect on the pretreatment cost, since heating
23 less volume will demand less energy. Beyond reducing the pretreatment cost, energy-
24 intensive techniques entail the application of a significant amount of mechanical

1 energy to the biomass. In these circumstances, the resulting shear-stress could act as a
2 pretreatment itself, enabling in some cases to completely dispense with the
3 pretreatment-related expenses.

4 In the present study, viability of microalgae was used in order to assess the
5 effect of the cross-flow filtration (CFF), as microalgae biomass concentration
6 technique, over the integrity of microalgae cells, whereas the effect of the
7 concentration step on the overall process was assessed in terms of anaerobic
8 biodegradability. Furthermore, an energy balance was carried out in order to assess
9 the relevance of using the CFF harvesting technique to concentrate microalgae
10 biomass prior to being fed to an anaerobic digester.

11 **2 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

12 *2.1 Microalgae biomass source.*

13 Fresh microalgae mainly consisting of *Chlorella spp.* (> 99 %), were obtained
14 from a pilot scale photobiorreactor (PBR) fed with the nutrient-rich effluent of an
15 anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) pilot plant. The PBR were inoculated with
16 microalgae originally collected from the walls of the secondary clarifier in the
17 “Barranco del Carraixet” WWTP (Alboraya, Valencia). Further details on the AnMBR
18 and the PBR pilot plants can be found in (Giménez et al., 2011) and (González-Camejo
19 et al., 2017), respectively. Both pilot plants are property of Calagua research group and
20 are located at the “Barranco del Carraixet” Wastewater Treatment Plant (Valencia,
21 Spain).

22 *2.2 Experimental Set-Up*

1 The system consisted of a cross-flow ultrafiltration skid which was directly fed
2 with fresh microalgae. The skid was equipped with a CFF tubular module containing
3 ultrafiltration membrane fibres with a molecular weight cut-off of 500 kDa (KOCH
4 ROMICON® 2", Koch membrane technology) and an effective filtration area of 1 m².
5 The filtration skid also included a centrifugal pump to provide a high flux through the
6 membrane fibres in order to promote the shear conditions necessary to remove the
7 fouling layer from the membrane surface, and a 20 L buffer tank to feed the pump and
8 to receive the recycled retentate. The system operated at a constant pressure drop
9 through the membrane cartridge of 1.4 bar, yielding a constant permeate flux of 11.3
10 L·m⁻³·h⁻¹ in the range of concentration tested. A level indicator and a turbidity sensor
11 (TSS) were installed on the buffer tank in order to control the fresh microalgae feeding
12 and to monitor the solids concentration, respectively.

13 2.3 *Experimental Procedure*

14 In order to assess the effect of the CFF harvesting technique on the microalgae
15 cell wall integrity, a total of 132 L of fresh microalgae with an original concentration of
16 0.691 g VS·L⁻¹ were fed to the harvesting system and concentrated up to around 9 g
17 VS·L⁻¹. This operation mode enabled to operate above the harvesting-system priming
18 volume (5 L) until the end of the process, yielding a final volume of around 10 L of
19 concentrated broth. Initially, the harvesting system was continuously topped up with
20 fresh microalgae from the PBR until the VS concentration reached around 3 g VS·L⁻¹.
21 Afterwards, the fresh microalgae feeding was stopped and the level of the buffer tank
22 started to decrease as the harvesting remained turned on, until a final concentration
23 of around 9 g VS·L⁻¹ was achieved. During the operation, 4 different samples of

1 microalgae biomass were collected at different times including fresh microalgae from
2 the PBR and the retentate from the buffer tank at around 3, 6 and 9 g VS·L⁻¹, that were
3 tagged as C1, and C2, C3 and C4, respectively. In addition, permeate samples were
4 collected simultaneously in order to evaluate the retention capacity of the cross-flow
5 ultrafiltration membrane.

6 2.4 *Analytical Methods.*

7 The chemical oxygen demand was measured in the total (T-COD) and in the
8 soluble (S-COD) fractions, and in the permeate (P-COD). Soluble fraction was obtained
9 after centrifugation (Eppendorf, 12000xg, 15 minutes). Total and volatile solids, and
10 sulphate concentration were determined according to the Standard Methods (Eaton et
11 al., 2005). Proteins and total sugars were determined in the soluble fraction (S-Pro and
12 S-CH, respectively) and in the permeate (P-Pro and P-CH, respectively). A modified
13 Lowry method (Lowry et al., 1951) was used for proteins quantification by using an
14 analytical kit commercialised by Sigma-Aldrich, whereas total sugars were determined
15 according to the Dubois method (DuBois et al., 1956).

16 2.5 *Cell viability*

17 Cell viability assays were performed in duplicate using SYTOX Green DNA
18 staining dye (Invitrogen S7020). 0.1 µL of SYTOX Green 5 mM was added to 50 µL of
19 250-400 mg·L⁻¹ suspended solids concentration of microalgae culture. As the SYTOX
20 Green is light-sensitive, the samples were incubated in the dark during 5 minutes.
21 Samples were excited using a fluorescence microscope (DM2500, Leica, Germany)
22 equipped with a filter set at 450 – 490 nm and 515 nm for excitation and emission,

1 respectively. More than 200 cells were counted for viability calculation in a Neubauer
2 counting chamber for each experiment.

3 2.6 *Biomethane potential tests*

4 Biodegradability of microalgae biomass was assessed in terms of biomethane
5 potential, considering that the theoretical specific methane potential per gram of COD
6 is 350 STP mL CH₄. Biomethane potential tests were carried out in triplicate for each
7 sample using an Automated Methane Potential Test System (AMPTS II, BioProcess
8 Control, Sweden) at 35°C. The organic load added to each bottle was exactly the same
9 (0.68 g COD), regardless of the microalgae biomass concentration and was calculated
10 on the basis of the less concentrated microalgae biomass sample, by adjusting the
11 total volume of the experiment to 1 litre and setting an inoculum to substrate ratio
12 (I/S) of 2. In order to add the same organic load to each bottle, the volume of
13 microalgae biomass added varied depending on the concentration of each microalgae
14 biomass sample. Samples were seeded with anaerobic sludge coming from an
15 industrial anaerobic digester treating municipal sewage from the “Barranco del
16 Carraixet” WWTP in Alboraya, Valencia. Furthermore, nutrients and trace elements,
17 and phosphate buffer were added in order to avoid growth limitation and inhibition by
18 acidification, respectively. The nutrient stock solution consisted of (g.L⁻¹): NH₄Cl (170),
19 CaCl₂·2H₂O (8), MgSO₄·7H₂O (9) and the trace element stock solution contained (g.L⁻¹):
20 FeCl₃·4H₂O (2), CoCl₂·6H₂O (2), MnCl₂·4H₂O (0.5), CuCl₂·2H₂O (30), ZnCl₂ (50), H₃BO₃
21 (50), (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂·4H₂O (90), Na₂SeO₃·5H₂O (100), NiCl₂·6H₂O (50), EDTA (1), HCl 36%
22 (1 ml.L⁻¹), Resazurine (0.5). The pH buffer stock solution was composed of
23 K₂HPO₄·3H₂O (45.65 g.L⁻¹) and NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O (31.20 g.L⁻¹). 6 mL of nutrient solution,

1 0.6 mL of trace elements solution and 50 mL of buffer solution per litre of microalgae
2 biomass were dosed to each sample .

3 **3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

4 *3.1 Microalgae biomass viability & Biodegradability.*

5 In the present study, the effect of CFF harvesting technique on microalgae cell
6 wall integrity was evaluated in terms of viability and biodegradability. To do so,
7 microalgae biomass samples with different concentration degrees (C1 to C4) were
8 collected at different times during harvesting. Table 1 shows the average
9 characterisation of the different microalgae biomass samples used in the present
10 study. Standard deviation (SD) of triplicates is also shown.

11 Viability revealed that the CFF harvesting equipment used in the present study
12 had a clear effect on the microalgae cell-wall integrity, since the viability decreased
13 from 89,0 % (C1) to 38,1 % (C4).

14 In addition, a good linear positive correlation ($R^2 = 0,9747$) was found between
15 the non-viable cells percentage ($[1 - V]\%$) and the biodegradability (BD %) of the
16 different samples, evidencing that the biodegradability of microalgae biomass was
17 dependent on the cell-wall integrity. The data were adjusted by a least squares
18 regression analysis to the Equation 1:

$$BD\% = 0.8196 \cdot [1 - V]\% + 2.9542 \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

19 (Prajapati et al., 2014) suggested in their study regarding anaerobic
20 biodegradability of different *Chlorella species* (i.e. *chlorella minutissima*, *pyrenoidosa*
21 and *vulgaris*), that some microalgae cells might had been broken during overnight
22 gravity settling, since they observed an unusually high initial methane production in

1 the BMP experiments that resulted in anaerobic biodegradabilities between 22.8 to
2 31.9 %. However, microalgae cell-integrity data, both before and after the harvesting
3 step, were not furnished in this study. Neither did the authors provide the biomass
4 concentration degree achieved with gravity settling as harvesting method. (Mahdy et
5 al., 2014) reported a biodegradability value of 54 % for fresh *Chlorella vulgaris* biomass
6 after being concentrated up to 22.3 g COD·L⁻¹ by centrifugation at 5000 rpm during 15
7 minutes. The authors agreed that this biodegradability value was higher than other
8 values reported in literature, although they did not hypothesized about a possible
9 explanation to this unexpected result. Also (Mendez et al., 2013) reported a
10 biodegradability value of 39.7 % for *Chlorella vulgaris* biomass concentrated up to 24.9
11 g COD·L⁻¹, although the authors did not provide any details about the harvesting
12 technique used.

13 The lack of homogeneity in literature regarding the anaerobic biodegradability
14 values for fresh *Chlorella vulgaris* biomass states that microalgae final biodegradability
15 not only depends on its composition and the pretreatment used, but there might also
16 be a contribution from the harvesting step. This underlying effect of the harvesting
17 step on the final biodegradability might be related to the effect of the technique used
18 on the integrity of the cell wall and on the stress induced over microalgae. Therefore,
19 in the light of these results, harvesting should be considered as a pretreatment itself
20 enabling, in some cases, to dispense with subsequent expensive pretreatments to
21 break the cell-wall.

22 In contrast, the COD mass balance stated that organic matter solubilisation was
23 not linked to neither viability nor biodegradability. Thus, generation of soluble organic
24 matter accounting for a 1.18-fold increase in the S-COD/T-COD ratio only took place

1 from C1 to C2 (see Table 2), i.e. as long as fresh algae were fed to the harvesting
2 system. The further increase in S-COD concentration in C3 and C4 (see Table 1) was
3 explained by the sole accumulation of the S-COD already present in the system. No
4 generation was observed indicating that, unlike biodegradability, solubilisation of
5 organic matter was not related to cell-wall disruption. Alternatively, it is hypothesized
6 that solubilisation took place as a response to the more stressful conditions prevailing
7 on the harvesting system, that promoted the release of soluble microbial products
8 (SMP) likely as a protection/survival strategy which contributed to increase the S-COD.
9 Extracellular polymeric substances (EPS) were not measured in the fresh microalgae
10 culture. Therefore, the origin of the SMP (whether it was EPS or intracellular
11 compounds being released following the cell-wall disruption) is not clear. In any case,
12 these SMP built up within the system due to the high retention capacity of the
13 ultrafiltration membranes, as evidenced by the steadiness of the COD and proteins
14 concentrations in the permeate (see Table 1) in spite of their accumulation in the
15 retentate, resulting in retention efficiencies of 98,4 % and 92,8 %, respectively. Results
16 regarding total sugars concentration in the supernatant of the centrifuged samples
17 were controversial, since the value was higher than the COD concentration (data not
18 shown). This error was attributed to the complex matrix of the supernatant which
19 interfered in the colorimetric determination.

20 This hypothesis is also supported by the S-COD fraction associated to the
21 proteins in the soluble phase ($S-COD_{Pro}/S-COD$; a COD/Proteins ratio of $2.43 \text{ g COD} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$
22 VS has been considered (Sialve et al., 2009). In spite of an initial decrease, $S-COD_{Pro}/S-$
23 COD finally reached a similar value to that of the fresh sample (see Table 2), indicating
24 that both the S-COD and the $S-COD_{Pro}$ concentrations increased in the same

1 proportion. Accordingly, the concentration factors achieved for the COD (F_{COD}) in the
2 supernatant of the different centrifuged samples, with regard to the fresh microalgae
3 culture (C1), were similar to those achieved for proteins (F_{PRO}). Total sugars
4 concentration factors (F_{CH}) were also calculated in spite of the controversial results
5 obtained for the total sugars absolute concentration values. F_{CH} were slightly higher
6 than F_{COD} and F_{PRO} , suggesting that the accumulation of sugars within the system
7 followed a similar trend to that of proteins.

8 These results state that the microalgae cell-wall breakage was enough to
9 enable anaerobic microorganism to access and degrade the inner organic compounds
10 of the former, even though these inner compounds were not completely released into
11 the broth. Presumably, cell-wall breakage yielded microalgae cells permeable to
12 anaerobic microorganisms, which were able to get into the microalgae and degrade
13 some biodegradable compounds that were not accessible in intact cells. Anaerobic
14 microorganisms invading microalgae cells rather than microalgae inner compounds
15 being released to the broth can be proposed as a more suitable hypothesis since, as
16 stated previously, S-COD generation only took place from C1 to C2, whereas
17 biodegradability was strongly correlated with the percentage of non-viable microalgae
18 cells.

19 Both the viability and the biodegradability trends, regarding the concentration
20 time or degree, were non-linear (see Table 1). In both cases, the higher increase from
21 C3 to C4 than from C1 to C2 or from C2 to C3 evidenced a higher impact of the CFF
22 harvesting technique over both the viability and the biodegradability percentages of
23 the microalgae biomass as the concentration rose. Two major contributors to the
24 observed trend were identified. On the one hand, it was hypothesized that the

1 increase in the S-COD was related to an initial release and further concentration of
2 SMP. Thus, the increase in the SMP concentration led to an increase in the viscosity of
3 the sample which promoted harsher shear-stress conditions as a result of the higher
4 flow resistance through the centrifugal pump and/or through the cross-flow
5 ultrafiltration membrane.

6 In this regard, (Scarsella et al., 2012) studied the effect of the mechanical stress
7 produced by several kinds of pumps on microalgae biomass integrity. According to
8 these authors, culture circulation establishes a shear field whose effect may vary from
9 beneficial to deleterious, according to the shear sensitivity, which depends on the
10 microalgae strain, the shear regime and the environmental conditions. They found that
11 centrifugal pumps have a significant impact on the microalgae integrity. Specifically,
12 microalgae *Chlorella vulgaris* appeared to be weaker than *Scenedesmus dimorphus* as
13 evidenced by an optical density reduction in the case of the former, following the
14 application of a similar mechanical stress. Specific photosynthetic activity remained
15 constant, indicating that surviving cells preserved their activity.

16 On the other hand, the specific power supply per unit of volume of the
17 concentrated microalgae suspension increased as the volume decreased, since the
18 number of passes through the harvesting system increased from 1 pass every 5
19 minutes to 3 passes per minute, inducing a higher mechanical stress over the
20 microalgae biomass. Accordingly, (Alías et al., 2004) gathered results from the diatom
21 *Pheadactylum tricornutum* circulating through different pumps. The authors found a
22 higher decay in biomass concentration and in the ratio of the maximum photosystem II
23 quantum yield when cultures were circulated with centrifugal pumps. They observed

1 that damage to cells increased with both the shear rate in the impeller and the
2 increase of the number of passes through the cavity pump.

3 As well as reducing the viability and increasing the biodegradability of
4 microalgae biomass, there are several effects related to biomass concentration using
5 CFF that should be taken into account when assessing continuous anaerobic digestion
6 of microalgae. First of all, concentrating the microalgae biomass would entail a
7 reduction in the daily flow-rate to the digester whilst keeping the organic load
8 constant. Furthermore, and since sulphate is a soluble compound present in the
9 culture coming from the PBR (González-Camejo et al., 2017), the sulphate load to the
10 anaerobic digester would be reduced, resulting in an increased COD to sulphate ratio.
11 Dissimilatory sulphate reduction to sulphide is carried out by sulphate reducing
12 bacteria (SRB) which perform anaerobic respiration rather than fermentation.
13 Stoichiometrically, 2 grams of COD are consumed by SRB in order to dissimilatory
14 reduce one gram of sulphur. Respiration, even using sulphate as electron acceptor, is
15 more efficient than fermentation, which enables SRB to outcompete methanogenic
16 archaea (MA) both from kinetic and thermodynamical points of view (Lens et al.,
17 1998). Therefore, the biodegradable COD would preferentially be consumed by SRB
18 rather than MA, for COD/ S-SO₄ ratios below 2.

19 For COD/S-SO₄ ratios of 2 and above, there would theoretically be enough COD
20 to reduce all sulphate, enabling MA to consume the leftover biodegradable COD that
21 would alternatively end-up as methane. In the present study, methane production will
22 start at a microalgae biomass concentration above 0.116 % (w/v).

23 In the present study, the methane production from the fresh microalgae
24 biomass resulted in a biodegradability of 9.3 %, even though the COD/S-SO₄ ratio was

1 lower than 2. It was hypothesized that the use of an inoculum with a virtually
2 inexistent sulphidogenic activity allowed the MA to take advantage of the COD present
3 before a well-established SRB community was developed (Giménez et al., 2011).
4 However, this behaviour diverts from what it could be expected in continuous
5 digesters, where SRB would outcompete MA (Giménez et al., 2011; Lens et al., 1998).

6 In addition, methane is produced by MA within the liquid face. Methane
7 diffuses through the liquid bulk and is further distributed between both the liquid and
8 gas phases until the equilibrium is reached. The solubility equilibrium of a gas in a
9 liquid is governed by the Henry's law. Therefore, the dissolved methane concentration
10 can be calculated by means of the equilibrium law as the saturation concentration as
11 long as there is a good mass transfer between both liquid and gas phases. If the system
12 is not properly mixed and the mass transfer is deficient, the liquid phase will probably
13 be oversaturated with methane. As a result, the lower the volume to be treated, the
14 lower the methane loss with the effluent, regardless of the total methane production.

15 Figure 4 shows the influent biodegradable COD fate depending on the biomass
16 concentration achieved during the harvesting step. The contribution of the influent
17 biodegradable COD to the different sinks have been calculated according to the
18 previously exposed premises (details on how to quantify each contribution will be
19 given in section "3.2 Energy Considerations", Equations (5 to 9). Briefly, biodegradable
20 COD will preferentially be consumed by SRB (COD-SRB), as long as sulphate is present.
21 It has been assumed that all sulphate will be reduced by SRB, entailing a COD
22 consumption of $2 \text{ g COD}\cdot\text{g}^{-1} \text{ S}$ (Lens et al., 1998). The remaining biodegradable COD will
23 be available for MA, which will be transformed into methane. A fraction of the
24 produced methane will remain dissolved in the liquid (COD-DCH₄) according to Henry's

1 equilibrium law. In order to calculate the dissolved methane, a methane fraction in the
2 biogas of 0.67 is assumed as a typical value (Passos et al., 2014b).

3 Finally, the remaining fraction of the produced methane will end up in the
4 biogas (COD-BG CH₄). As it can be seen, for the raw biomass (C1), the influent
5 biodegradable COD is completely consumed by SRB (COD-SRB), whereas for the most
6 concentrated sample (C4), 98.1 % of the biodegradable influent COD is devoted to
7 methane production by MA. A small fraction of the methane produced (0.8 %) remains
8 dissolved (COD-DCH₄), and the rest is recovered with the biogas (COD-BGCH₄).

9 3.2 Energy Considerations.

10 An energy balance was carried out to assess the interest of using the CFF
11 harvesting technique to concentrate microalgae biomass prior to being fed to an
12 anaerobic digester. The following assumptions were made in order to perform the
13 energy balance:

- 14 ■ Neither microalgae biomass growth nor anaerobic digestion energetic
15 requirements (namely mixing and pumping, and aeration when applicable)
16 were considered in this study.
- 17 ■ All the biogas produced is fuelled to a CHP system. A microturbine was selected
18 as CHP system which features electric and thermal efficiencies of 26.7 and 41.1
19 %, respectively (U.S Department of Energy Fact sheet series, n.d.).
- 20 ■ Thermal energy production is devoted to warm the microalgae biomass up to
21 mesophilic conditions (i.e. 35 °C) prior to being fed to the anaerobic digester.
22 The density and specific heat of microalgae biomass were supposed to be the
23 same as those of water. Heat loss through the anaerobic digester wall was

1 considered (heat-loss through neither top nor bottom have been considered
 2 (Passos and Ferrer, 2014)). Anaerobic digester was assumed to have cylindrical
 3 geometry with a diameter to height ratio of 2:1. Digester dimensions were
 4 determined based on the useful volume for a HRT of 20 days.

- 5 ■ All calculations were made on the basis of a daily microalgae biomass
 6 production of 1 m³.

7 Thermal energy requirements ($E_{i,T}$) were calculated as the addition of the
 8 energy required to warm the microalgae biomass up to mesophilic conditions and the
 9 energy loss through the digester wall according to equation (1), whereas electric
 10 energy requirements ($E_{i,E}$) only accounted for the electric energy demand from the
 11 harvesting unit (equation (2)):

$$E_{i,T} (MJ/d) = \rho \cdot Q \cdot \gamma \cdot (T_d - T_a) + k \cdot A \cdot (T_d - T_a) \cdot 86.4 \quad \text{Equation (2)}$$

$$E_{i,E} (MJ/d) = E_{cons,CFF} \cdot Q \quad \text{Equation (3)}$$

12 Specific energy consumption data in a CFF unit ($E_{cons,CFF}$) reported by
 13 (Danquah et al., 2009) have been used in the present work. These authors reported a
 14 net energy consumption of 7.42 MJ·m⁻³ of permeate for a CFF unit which consisted in a
 15 4 GPM *Pellicon cassette system* (Millipore, DUOBLOC TM, USA), harvesting *Tetraselmis*
 16 *suecica*.

17 Moreover, both electric ($E_{o,E}$) and thermal ($E_{o,T}$) energy productions were
 18 calculated from the daily methane production recovered with the biogas ($P_{BG}^{CH_4}$) and
 19 the electric and thermal efficiencies of the CHP unit selected, respectively (see
 20 Equations (3) and (4)).

$$E_{o,E} (MJ/d) = P_{BG}^{CH_4} \cdot \xi^{CH_4} \cdot \eta_{CHP}^{Electric} \quad \text{Equation (4)}$$

$$E_{o,T} (MJ/d) = P_{BG}^{CH_4} \cdot \xi^{CH_4} \cdot \eta_{CHP}^{Thermal} \quad \text{Equation (5)}$$

1 A lower heating value of $35.8 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for the methane was considered for the
2 calculations (Tchobanoglous and Burton, 1998).

3 Total methane production was calculated from the total amount of COD
4 available for methanogens, by subtracting the COD consumed by SRB to the total
5 biodegradable COD, according to Equation (5):

$$P_T^{CH_4} (m^3 CH_4 STP/d) = ([COD]_0 \cdot \%BD - 2 \cdot [S - SO_4]) \cdot Q \cdot Y_{Theo}^{CH_4} \quad \text{Equation (6)}$$

6 where %BD is the percentage of biodegradability of the microalgae biomass
7 interpolated from the values previously reported and $S-SO_4$ is the sulphur
8 concentration as sulphate ($\text{kg S}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). The factor multiplying sulphate concentration
9 term accounts for the stoichiometric amount of COD consumed to reduce sulphate
10 (Lens et al., 1998).

11 Dissolved methane was excluded from the total methane production for the
12 energy output calculation (see Equation (6)). However, a deeper insight into the energy
13 balance of dissolved methane recovery process is necessary to elucidate whether the
14 biological oxidation of dissolved methane, just to prevent its emission, would be a
15 more suitable option.

$$P_{BG}^{CH_4} (m^3 CH_4 STP/d) = P_T^{CH_4} - P_D^{CH_4} \quad \text{Equation (7)}$$

16 For the dissolved methane estimation (see equations (7) to (9)), it was assumed
17 that the solubility of methane in the effluent of the digester was similar to that of pure
18 water. Also, a methane fraction of 0.67 was selected for the gas phase.

$$P_D^{CH_4} (m^3 CH_4 STP/d) = Q \cdot \frac{x^{CH_4} \cdot M^W}{(1 - x^{CH_4})} \cdot R \cdot T \quad \text{Equation (8)}$$

$$P \cdot y^{CH_4} = H^{CH_4}(T) \cdot x^{CH_4} \quad \text{Equation (9)}$$

$$H^{CH_4}(T) = 10^{\left[\frac{-675.74}{T(K)} + 6.88\right]} \quad \text{Equation (10)}$$

1 where x^{CH_4} and y^{CH_4} stand for the molar fraction of methane in the liquid and
 2 in the gas phases, respectively. M^W stands for the molarity of water ($55.5 \text{ kmol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), R
 3 ($0.082057 \text{ m}^3\cdot\text{atm}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}\cdot\text{kmol}^{-1}$) stands for the universal constant of ideal gases, P (atm)
 4 stands for pressure and $H^{CH_4}(T)$ (atm^{-1}) stands for the temperature-dependent
 5 Henry's constant for methane (Tchobanoglous and Burton, 1998).

6 The electric and thermal energy balances were assessed in terms of the net
 7 electric and thermal energy demands (NEED and NTED, respectively) according to
 8 Equations (10) and (11), which were calculated in the basis of the electric and thermal
 9 energy inputs (see Equations (1) and (2)) and outputs (see Equations (8) and (9))
 10 previously described. Furthermore, the total net energy demand (NED), was calculated
 11 as the addition of both the net electric and thermal energy demands (see Equation
 12 (12)).

$$NEED (MJ/d) = E_{i, E} (MJ/d) - E_{o, E} (MJ/d) \quad \text{Equation (11)}$$

$$NTED (MJ/d) = E_{i, T} (MJ/d) - E_{o, T} (MJ/d) \quad \text{Equation (12)}$$

$$NED (MJ/d) = NEED (MJ/d) + NTED (MJ/d) \quad \text{Equation (13)}$$

13 Figure 5 (a) shows that the electric energy requirements increase as the
 14 microalgae concentration increases, as a result of the increase in the volume to be
 15 filtered. On the contrary, the electric energy production increases as the
 16 biodegradability and the availability of COD to the MA increases, as a result of a higher
 17 methane production, bringing about a decrease in the NEED for a microalgae biomass
 18 COD concentration higher than 1 % (w/v). Figure 5 (b) shows that the thermal energy
 19 requirements decrease significantly as the microalgae concentration increases, since

1 the volume to be warmed up is lower. Furthermore, the higher methane production
2 increases the thermal energy production, both contributing to decrease the NTED.
3 Figure 5 (c) shows that in spite of the increase in the NEED for biomass COD
4 concentrations lower than 1 % (w/v), its contribution to the NED is not really
5 significant, as compared to the NTED contribution. As a result, the NED decreases with
6 the biomass COD concentration, and this decrease is more pronounced for biomass
7 COD concentrations higher than 1 % (w/v). Nonetheless, the NED remained positive in
8 the whole range of concentrations evaluated, corresponding the lowest NED value to
9 the most concentrated sample (C4), that accounted for 11.9 MJ·m⁻³.

10 Electric and thermal efficiencies were defined as the electric and thermal
11 energy production to consumption ratio (E_o/E_i), respectively. As shown in Figure 6, the
12 highest electric and thermal efficiencies correspond to the most concentrated sample,
13 accounting for 20.1 and 25.2 %, respectively, yielding an overall energetic efficiency of
14 22.9 %. It is worth to mention that, in the present study, a threshold concentration
15 value at around 1 % was observed, above which the thermal efficiency was higher than
16 the electric efficiency.

17 **4 CONCLUSIONS**

18 The effect of cross-flow filtration over microalgae integrity was evaluated in
19 terms of cell viability and biodegradability. The concentration achieved affected both
20 viability and biodegradability of biomass, which were linearly correlated. It was
21 hypothesized that the accumulation of organic polymers during the harvesting
22 promoted harsher shear-stress conditions. Furthermore, the specific energy supply
23 increased as the total volume decreased. The energy demand turned out to be positive
24 in the whole range of concentrations evaluated. The lowest energy demand

1 corresponded to the most concentrated sample and accounted for 11.9 MJ·m⁻³,
2 yielding and an energetic efficiency of 22.9%.

3 **5 APPENDIX A: SUPPLEMENTARY DATA**

4 E-supplementary data for this work can be found in e-version of this paper
5 online

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1

2 Figure 1. COD fate depending on the influent T-COD concentration ([T-COD]₀). COD-SRB: COD consumed by SRB;
 3 COD-DCH₄: COD associated to dissolved methane; COD-BG CH₄: COD associated to methane in the biogas.

1 Figure 2. Electric (a) and thermal (b) energy balance assessment, and energy requirements (c). NEED: Net Electric
 2 Energy Demand; NTED: Net Thermal Energy Demand; NED: Net Energy Demand.

1

2 Figure 3. Electric, thermal and overall energy efficiencies.

1 Table 1. Microalgae biomass samples characterisation (Mean \pm SD).

Parameters	Units	Samples			
		C1	C2	C3	C4
Sampling time	hours	0	10.28	10.85	11.05
viability	%	89.0 \pm 7.5	85.1 \pm 8.5	79.5 \pm 6.1	38.1 \pm 10.7
Biodegradability	%	9.3 \pm 8.3	14.2 \pm 8.3	24.2 \pm 8.4	52.8 \pm 8.3
TS	mg TS·L ⁻¹	1678 \pm 11	5517 \pm 17	8001 \pm 40	9871 \pm 10
VS	mg VS·L ⁻¹	691 \pm 14	4305 \pm 25	6657 \pm 41	8430 \pm 19
T-COD	mg O ₂ ·L ⁻¹	810 \pm 7	6627 \pm 196	10213 \pm 133	12593 \pm 133
S-COD	mg O ₂ ·L ⁻¹	210 \pm 16	2033 \pm 34	3137 \pm 111	3750 \pm 62
P-COD	mg O ₂ ·L ⁻¹	67.3 \pm 2.1	45.6 \pm 1.8	60.8 \pm 1.5	61.2 \pm 1.8
S-Pro	mg Pr·L ⁻¹	20.2 \pm 0.6	142.8 \pm 1.1	260.1 \pm 7.1	365.5 \pm 14.1
P-Pro	mg Pr·L ⁻¹	18.9 \pm 0.0	24.4 \pm 1.9	23.6 \pm 0.0	26.5 \pm 3.2
P-CH	mg CH·L ⁻¹	21.9 \pm 1.9	5.6 \pm 0.3	17.4 \pm 1.4	15.0 \pm 1.6
S-SO ₄	mg S·L ⁻¹	187.7 \pm 2.3	185.9 \pm 2.4	182.2 \pm 2.2	184.6 \pm 2.3

2

- 1 Table 2. Soluble/total COD and proteins-related COD fraction in the soluble phase, and
- 2 concentration factors achieved for COD (F_{COD}), proteins (F_{PRO}) and total sugars (F_{CH})
- 3 with regard to the fresh microalgae culture.

Sample	$\frac{S - COD}{T - COD}$	$\frac{S - COD_{Pro}}{S - COD}$	F_{COD}	F_{PRO}	F_{CH}
	%				
C1	25.9±2.2	23.1±2.5	-	-	-
C2	30.7±1.4	17.1±0.4	8.3±0.8	7.1±0.3	11.5±2.1
C3	30.7±1.5	20.1±1.3	12.5±1.5	12.9±0.7	15.9±3.2
C4	29.8±0.8	23.7±1.3	15.2±1.5	18.1±1.2	20.3±2.8

4